

The International Journal of Ambient Systems and Applications (IJASA)

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Scope & Topics

The International Journal of Ambient Systems and applications is a quarterly open access peer-reviewed journal that publishes articles which contribute new results in all areas of ambient Systems. The journal focuses on all technical and practical aspects of ambient Systems, networks, technologies and applications. The goal of this journal is to bring together researchers and practitioners from academia and industry to focus on advanced ambient Systems and establishing new collaborations in these areas.

Authors are solicited to contribute to this journal by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in ambient Systems.

Topics of interest include but are not limited to, the following

- Agent Systems, Intelligent Computing and Applications
- Autonomic Networks and Communications
- Cognitive wireless sensor network
- Context awareness, social sensing and inference
- Data Management
- Dependable, Reliable and Autonomic Computing
- Embedded Systems and Software
- Emerging Networking, Tracking and Sensing Technologies
- Ergonomics and product prototyping
- Healthcare Systems
- Intelligent and self-organizing transportation networks & services
- Multimedia and Social Computing
- Multimodal Interfaces
- Service and Semantic Computing
- Service Oriented Computing for Systems & Applications
- Smart Environments and Applications
- Systems Security and Privacy
- Systems Software Engineering
- Ubiquitous Computing and Applications
- Vehicular Networks and Applications

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers for this journal through **Email: ijasa@aircconline.com** or through **[Submission System](#)**. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this Journal.

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : April 09, 2022**
- Notification : May 09, 2022
- Final Manuscript Due : May 17, 2022
- Publication Date : Determined by the Editor-in-Chief

Contact Us

Here's where you can reach us : ijasa@aircconline.com